

ATTITUDES OF CUSTOMERS TOWARDS THE FIRST CHOICE OF SHOPPING MALLS IN NAVI MUMBAI

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ABSTRACT: Shopping mall is a group of retail stores under one roof .The fascinating retail location entails a need to manage shopping malls effectively to know the features that attract shopping mall visitors to visit shopping malls. The factors that affect store choice and draw customers to the shopping center include space, environment, convenience and an array of choice under one roof. The development of integrated shopping malls, retail chains and multi-brand outlets is evidence of consumer behaviour being favorable to the growing organized segment of the business. Space, ambience and convenience are start to play an important role in drawing customers. Malls, which are now committed by large outlets such as Westside and Lifestyle and are resided by a lot of Indian and international brands, are also being seen as image index for communities. Data were collected from shopping Malls in the state of Maharashtra, Navi Mumbai. The total number of respondents selected for this study is 300.A structured questionnaire has been employed for collecting the information from the sample respondents about their Personal profile. Factors influencing the customer to shop in the shopping malls of Navi Mumbai such as socio-economic profiles, income, frequency of visit, period of relationship between the respondents and shopping malls, purpose of visit, occasion to visit shopping malls are some of the aspects studied in the present study The objectives of this study is to investigate the attitudes towards the preference of Shopping Malls by the mall shoppers in the study area .The collected data was analyzed with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for windows.

Keywords: Shopping malls, shopping culture, consumer attitudes, shopping behavior

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays malls play a leading role in the life style of people living in metro cities which has greatly reformed the outlines of spending activities and malls are found almost everywhere. A shopping centre, shopping mall, or shopping plaza, is the modern adaptation of the historical marketplace. An important aspect of the current economic scenario in India is the emergence of organized retail. There has been considerable growth in organized retailing business in recent years and it is poised for much faster growth in the future. In the modern era people believe that the malls are best place to shop or hang out. It is not only a place to shop but also a place for social and recreational activities. The study revealed that the shopper's visit to the selected mall is mostly influenced by certain priorities in the minds of the customers. Organized retail chain and mall stores are mushrooming in all major cities and towns of India. Apart from private players in the organized retail chain business like 'Shoppers Stop', 'Spencer's', 'Food Bazar', 'Hyper city', 'Inorbit', 'Big Bazar', Wills Lifestyle and so on, major industrial houses like Tata, Birla, Reliance, Pantaloons Retail (India) Limited etc. have entered the retail business and have announced very ambitious future expansion plans. Multinational retailers are also coming to India to set up retail chains in collaboration with big Indian companies. Modern retail formats such as hypermarkets, superstores, discount stores, convenience stores are widely present in major cities of India.

Objectives of the study

1. To know the personal profile of the Sample Respondents in the study area.
2. To know the consumer attitudes towards preference or the first choice of Shopping Malls in Navi Mumbai

Area of study

The study conducted in Navi Mumbai. The data was collected from the shoppers of eighteen top malls of Navi Mumbai.

Methodology

The data in this study has been collected both from the primary and secondary sources. The present study specifically addresses the mall shoppers of Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, as no study in this area has been conducted so far. Convenient sampling method is used to collect primary data. The total number of respondents selected for this study is 300 and the sample respondents are from mall shoppers of eighteen malls in Navi Mumbai. A structured questionnaire has been employed for collecting the information from the respondents about their demographics and the consumer attitudes towards preference of Shopping Malls.

Review of Literature

1. Kothapalle inthiyaz (2017) the article titled "a study on attractiveness factors influencing shoppers' satisfaction, loyalty, and word of mouth in shopping malls at Bangalore city". The purpose of this research is to investigate the attractiveness factors influencing shoppers' satisfaction, loyalty, and word of mouth in Bangalore shopping mall centers. The independent variables were attractiveness factors represented by these variables namely aesthetic, convenience and accessibility, product variety, entertainment, and service quality. A purposive sampling technique was employed in this research. This research potentially contributes to shopping malls attractiveness factors and their impact on shoppers' satisfaction in shopping malls of Bangalore.

2. **Dr. A. Nirmal Raj (2016)** in his study titled "Probing the Factors Influencing Shoppers' Behaviour and its Impact on Shoppers' Loyalty – An Empirical Study with special reference to Shopping Malls in Chennai City". The purpose of this study is to investigate the shopping behaviour towards shopping malls with six important dimensions with special reference to Chennai city using structural equation modelling. The study also attempts to assist the retailers, mall designers, administrators, dealers and operators with a seamless mixture of necessary intelligence, in terms of customer's motivations, essential to offer the targeted customers so that the shopping mall can be operated with highest efficiency and performance.

3. **Satnam Kour Ubeja (2015)** the study titled "A Study of Customer Satisfaction in Shopping Malls: An Empirical Study" the author made an attempt to investigate the effects of sales promotion mix and marketing mix on customer satisfaction in shopping malls of Ujjain city and also study the variation of demographic variable. The study was conducted and visited on different malls and collected the data of sales promotion mix and marketing mix for customer satisfaction in Ujjain city. This study will be helpful for retailers to understand the level of satisfaction of the customer before deciding any type of sales promotion mix. With the help of this study they can also make some good marketing and promotional strategies and also helpful to understand the buyer's choice on the basis of gender.

Tools for Analysis

The factor analyses, the principal component method are applied to derive the predominant factor of consumer attitudes towards the preference of Shopping Malls. The twelve variables in the research instrument are subject to Extraction Method, Principal Component Analysis, and Rotation Method, Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Table 1
Personal profile of the Sample Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age wise distribution			
Less than 20	3	1	1
20 - 25	51	17	18
25 - 30	49	16	34
35 - 40	63	21	55
40 - 45	53	18	73
45 - 50	71	24	97
More than 50	10	3	100
Total	300	100	
Gender Wise Distribution			
Male	193	64	64
Female	107	36	100
Total	300	100	
Income Wise Distribution			
Less than 10000	28	9	9
10000 - 20000	12	4	13
20000 - 30000	44	15	28
30000 - 40000	73	24	52
40000 - 50000	66	22	74
50000 - 60000	49	16	90
Above 60000	28	10	100
Total	300	100	
Occupation Wise Distribution			
Students	28	9	9
Public servants	92	31	40
Private service	90	30	70
Teachers/Professors	58	19	89
Retired	3	1	90
Unemployed	2	1	91
Own Business	27	9	100
Total	300	100	

Education Wise Distribution			
Less than 10 th Grade	6	2	2
Metric	5	2	4
Higher Secondary	20	6	10
Diploma PG Diploma	34	11	21
Graduates	116	39	60
Post Graduates	80	27	87
Doctorate/CA/Doctors	39	13	100
Total	300	100	
Marital Status			
Married	263	88	88
Unmarried	28	9	97
Separated	9	3.0	100
Total	300	100	
Number of Family members			
Up to 2	18	6	6
2-4	83	28	34
4-6	139	46	80
6-8	36	12	92
Above 8	24	8	100
Total	300	100	

Source: Primary survey

The sample group consist of members at the age group of 45-50 (24%), 35-40 (21%), 40-45 (18%), 20-25 (17%), and 25-30 (16%), The sample group consist of only 3 percent aged more than 50 and only one percent aged less than 20 years. 64 percent of them are male and the remaining 36 percent are female. The income group of those visiting the Malls do differ which consist of respondents falls under the income range of Rs. 30000 – 45000 (24%), Rs.45000 – 60000 (22%), Rs.60000 – 75000 (16%), Rs.15000 – 30000 (15%), Rs.75000 – 90000 (8%) and less than Rs.15000 (4%). According to occupation of the respondents, Public servants are majority (31%), followed by Private Service (30%), Teachers and professors (19%), students and business people (9%), Retired and unemployed people (1%). With regards to the education, 39 percent of the sample respondents are Graduates, 27 percent Post Graduates, 13 percent professionals having Doctorate / CA / Doctors, 6 percent finished Higher Secondary and 2 percent each 10th Grade and Less than 10th Grade. The marital Status of the respondents indicates that 88 percent are married, 9 percent are unmarried and the remaining 3 percent are separated. With regards to the number of family members, 6 percent have the family size of the maximum of two members, 28 percent have 2-4 members, 46 percent have 4-6 members, 12 percent have 6-8 members and 8 percent have more than 8 members.

Preference of Shopping Malls

The decision of shopping range from the decision to go shopping, through the choice of shopping mall to which stores or tenants to visit, what to buy, where to stop for a rest, and so on. Information on malls' choice will be useful for practitioners to secure their position in the arena of competing shopping malls. Knowledge about motives underlying mall choice and about shoppers' preferences and behavior is beneficial in creating a demand-oriented mall environment and the right arrangement of tenants. When embarking on a shopping trip, individuals have to make several interdependent decisions. The degree of pre-planning that is involved may differ. Some individuals may prepare a detailed shopping list and plan exactly the sequence in which they intend to visit the stores. Other may not plan at all, except for having a very crude idea what kind of things they wish to do and then, they choose the shopping mall. In addition, they might consider how they can get there, and who will go with them. The travel party may also influence the choice of mall and what to do there. Previous shopping experiences with malls will influence future choices. The more satisfied an individual is with a mall based on previous shopping experiences, the more likely the individual will choose that mall again.

Table 2

Preference of Shopping Malls (First Choice to select)

Statements	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Many events & promotional activities in Shopping malls which attract me to visit there.	66.78	.000
Easy accessibility of different areas from parking to shopping	65.74	.000
Good range of brands	57.73	.000
Going to malls results in Impulsive buying behavior	49.71	.000
Wide-ranging choice of products as compared to traditional shops.	45.46	.000
The clarity of information is better in shopping malls.	44.71	.000
Comfortable and unperturbed while selection of goods because the toddler / kids shall be taken care of in the crèche / day care / children pen	43.52	.000

Shopping malls offer Memberships, to get discounts / packages for frequent goers etc.	41.33	.000
Flexibility of timings of shopping mall	41.01	.000
The capacity of the Shopping malls is limited and gets filled up very soon.	40.65	.000
The Shopping malls should be located in a convenient place	39.28	.000
There is an added attraction of supplementing services available in a Shopping malls which one can resort to after purchasing the products like Beauty parlors / Hair Salons, cafes/ restaurants etc	38.66	.000

Source: Derived

Preference of shopping malls may depend on certain priorities in the minds of the customers. The sample respondents' views on this respect are tested through 't' test and it shows that the statement many events & promotional activities in Shopping malls which attract one to visit there has top score of 66.78. The other statements as per order are Easy accessibility of different areas from parking to shopping (65.74), Good range of brands (57.73), Going to malls results in Impulsive buying behavior (49.71), Wide-ranging choice of products as compared to traditional shops (45.46), The clarity of information is better in shopping malls (44.71), Comfortable and unperturbed while selection of goods because the toddler / kids shall be taken care of in the crèche/day care/children pen (43.52), Shopping malls offer Memberships, to get discounts / packages for frequent goers etc (41.33), Flexibility of timings of shopping mall (41.01), The capacity of the Shopping malls is limited and gets filled up very soon (40.65), The Shopping malls should be located in a convenient place (39.28) and There is an added attraction of supplementing services available in a Shopping malls which one can resort to after purchasing the products like Beauty parlors / Hair Salons, cafes/ restaurants etc (38.66). Hence it is understood that the people give much importance to the promotional events of the shopping malls.

Table 3

Rotated Component Matrix for the preference of Malls

Statements	Components				
	1	2	3	4	5
Good range of branded products	.862	-.032	.010	-.243	.050
Shopping malls offer Memberships, to get discounts / packages for frequent goers etc.	.782	-.072	.189	.029	-.264
Many events & promotional activities in Shopping malls which attract me to visit there.	.578	.467	-.051	.019	.136
Wide-ranging choice of products as compared to traditional shops	-.119	.807	.013	.119	-.227
Spacious to accommodate number of people	.239	.783	-.092	.075	.262
Flexibility of timings of shopping mall	-.221	.571	.507	-.319	-.039
Comfortable and unperturbed while selection of goods because the toddler / kids shall be taken care of in the crèche / day care / children pen	.005	.006	.900	-.132	.029
There is an added attraction of supplementing services available in a Shopping malls which one can resort to after purchasing the products like Beauty parlors / Hair Salons, cafes/ restaurants etc	.235	-.075	.788	.297	.063
The Shopping malls should be located in a convenient place	-.109	.048	-.030	.832	.004
Easy accessibility of different areas from parking to shopping	-.060	.044	.049	.779	.169
Going to malls results in Impulsive buying behaviour	.053	.135	.228	.130	.864
The clarity of information is better in shopping malls	.369	.278	.298	-.117	-.630
% of variance	16.83	16.00	15.65	13.47	11.57
Cumulative Variance	16.83	32.83	48.48	61.95	73.52
% to total	23	22	21	18	16

Source: Derived

Brands and Offers: Due to the change in the life styles as well as increase in the disposable income among the people, there is a great demand for the branded products. Here the filtered statements are Good range of branded products (.862), Shopping malls offer Memberships, to get discounts / packages for frequent goers etc (.782) and Many events & promotional activities in Shopping malls which attract me to visit there (.578). This factor has a variance of 16.83 percent and contributes 23 percent to total.

Time and Space: Flexibility timings means the shopping malls are in open condition without any interval during the working hours and space refers to the spacious shops available within and also the space available for walking and chatting. The statements filtered here are Wide-ranging choice of products as compared to traditional shops (.807), Spacious to accommodate number of people (.783) and Flexibility of timings of shopping mall (.578). This factor has a variance of 16 percent and contributes 22 percent to total.

Care and Comfort: People generally prefer undisturbed shopping hours to choose the products of their needs and now a days the shopping malls are doing wonderful jobs by caring and engaging the kids separately. Here the statements filtered are Comfortable and unperturbed while selection of goods because the toddler / kids shall be taken care of in the crèche / day care / children pen (.900) and There is an added attraction of supplementing services available in a Shopping malls which one can resort to after purchasing the products like Beauty parlors / Hair Salons, cafes/ restaurants etc (.788). This factor has a variance of 15.65 percent and contributes 21 percent to total.

Convenient and Accessible: Convenience is the most important factor which decides the purchasing behavior of the young and old, rich and poor, employed and unemployed and so on. Here the statements consisting of The Shopping malls should be located in a convenient place (.832) and Easy accessibility of different areas from parking to shopping (.779). This factor has a variance of 13.47 percent and contributes 18 percent to total.

Impulsive and Informative: The modern malls are full of information which is visible everywhere so that the customers can get the easy accessibility of items by not wasting time and energy. At the same time it gives urge to buy even the unnecessary and unwanted items too. Here the selected statements are Going to malls results in Impulsive buying behavior (.864) and The clarity of information is better in shopping malls (-.630). This factor has a variance of 11.57 percent and contributes 16 percent to total.

Table 4

Component Transformation Matrix

Components	Brands and Offers	Time and Space	Care and Comfort	Convenient and Accessible	Impulsive and Informative
Brands and Offers	.671	.462	.513	-.222	-.158
Time and Space	-.289	.554	.269	.588	.438
Care and Comfort	-.006	-.655	.720	.177	.145
Convenient and Accessible	.682	-.225	-.381	.504	.292
Impulsive and Informative	-.042	.010	.036	.565	-.823

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Source: Derived

Brands and Offers has positive relationship with Brands and Offers and Care and Comfort, Time and Space has positive relationship with Time and Space and Convenient and Accessible, Care and Comfort has positive relationship with Care and Comfort and negative relationship with Time and Space, Convenient and Accessible has positive relationship with Brands and Offers and Convenient and Accessible and Impulsive and Informative has positive relationship with Convenient and Accessible and negative relationship with Impulsive and Informative as both are being contradictory to each other. On an overall assessment it is noted that there is positive association between Brands and Offers and Convenient and Accessible.

Suggestion

1. Know your customer. Make the habit of giving your customers what they want, they will do business and buy from the shop, the services provide should reflect your customers' needs and wants. Think from the customers' perspective show them, sell and say things that interest them this will create good image in the mind of customers ultimately increase the sales .
2. Value a regular customer by giving them offer, loyalty points and notifying them ahead of a flash sale on their mobile phone. Reach out to customers via SMS and emails. This makes it convenient for a customer to plan out a happy shopping experience.
3. Stay updated about your inventory stocks .All mall keepers need to manage inventory. The retailer who regularly watches the store's shelves and should maintain a proper balance between the right amount of stocks and customer demand.
4. Go for digital. Digitized information of inventory and shelf stocks, cash, and accounts along with multiple payment options makes it an effortless check out for the shopper.

Conclusion

Draw attention to the brand or product effectively in a shopping mall and reach a vast amount of visitors and potential customers in highly frequented centers. Due to the high jump present in shopping malls, companies are able to address a wide target group. Consumers in shopping centers are in a spending mood and usually possess a higher disposable income therefore typically reacting openly to on-site promotions. People give much importance to the promotional events of the shopping malls. Factor analysis applied for the preference of malls falls under the heads Brands and Offers, Time and Space, Care and Comfort, Convenient and Accessible and Impulsive and Informative and on an overall assessment it is noted that there is a positive association between Brands and Offers and Convenient and Accessible.

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